

SEMANTIC FIELD OF THE LEXICAL UNITS EXPRESSING HUMAN SPIRITUAL STATE IN THE ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Annotation: *In sociolinguistics, Eckert has begun to ask how social meaning in variation is connected to affective meaning. She poses such questions as if social meaning leads to affective meaning, whether children learn social uses of variation through affect before extrapolating to categories of speakers, and whether affective meaning is actually separable from social meaning. Part of the complication is that display rules of emotions – and probably the experiences of emotions themselves – are not independent of a person's place in the social order. Eckert's examples include Colette, when being "negative" than when being "nice". In our analyses, we can't really separate the affective meaning from social categories like gender.*

Keywords: *rage; sorrow; fearless; idioms; fearsomeness; affect; hateful.*

The emotions that are studied do change when one switches to naturalistic data. While acted data tends to investigate *rage* and *sorrow*, naturalistic data expresses *irritation* and *resignation*.

Of course the research goals of these programs are quite different: one of them is to catch the meaning of human psychology, the second is to create applications that can detect and respond to human emotions. As Scherer suggests, however, a lack of understanding of the psychological theory is to hamper any kind of attempts to make detection better

Several studies have found that women score higher men in at least some areas of emotional intelligence. A variety of issues and scientific works may lead to this outcome. For instance, women typically excel at correctly classifying facial emotions and distinguishing among various emotions. That's why, it has been established that gender correlates with emotional intelligence and that women on average perform better than men.

However, although women on average score higher than men on emotional intelligence tests, more investigation needs to address potential group differences

in emotional intelligence in order to ascertain that no adverse impact exists. An unanswered question connecting with emotional intelligence and gender is whether or not women utilize emotional intelligence to a greater degree than their male counterparts. Although there is little theoretical development linked to gender interactions in emotional intelligence, some related theory and empirical findings support such a claim. For example, women tend to be more empathetic and emotional than men and were found to be more verbally explicit about feelings and passions than men, According to Thayer & Johnson people generally self-disclose more to women than to men. Andersen & Bem considered women also tend to self-disclose more and are considered more responsive conversation partners than men. Finally, women may be more likely than men to provide emotional appraisal social support, Shumaker & Hill determined. It could be complicated to argue that males and females don't differ in how they react to emotions. Janz argues that men tend to suppress most of their feelings, a phenomenon known as "restrictive emotionality." Although these gender differences may be tangential to emotional intelligence, they help to bolster the argument that the relationship between emotional intelligence and certain outcomes may depend on the gender of the subject.

Learning emotional differences between men and women are plentiful. Scientists' researches lead us to believe that women are more emotional than men, or at least are more emotionally expressive. A common assumption exists that has transpired over the years with regard to women being more emotionally expressive than men. Many investigates have been conducted, examining emotional expressiveness in men and women and there is a fairly substantial body of research presenting that women are the more emotionally expressive gender. In addition to this there are certain emotions that have been stereotypically related to each gender. Emotions of happiness, sadness and fear are believed to be more characteristic of women, whereas men are believed to be more characteristically angry [2]

It has also been found that the emotions of *happiness*, *sadness* and *fear* are believed to be more characteristic of women, whereas men are believed to be more characteristically *angry*. These stereotypes have provided a basis for society to deem what is and is not socially acceptable for males and females in displaying emotions.

According to the researches we conclude that men do not show their weakness and they get used to not expressing some negative emotions such as *fear* and *depression* however, women are more emotional than men so they have better

conceptual knowledge in emotional terms such as *happy, joyful, glad, excitement, nervous, tired* and so on.

We try to avoid analyzing all the different morphological variations of the same underlying root in order to analyze of emotion words and we use an article "The Language of Emotions: An Analysis of a Semantic Field" by P. N. Johnson-Laird and Keith Oatley [3]. This article provides us with a helpful initial clarification concerning which terms are truly part of the emotional lexicon and we analyze their opinions with comparing Uzbek language. The lexicon of emotions does indeed contain words from all the main categories: nouns, verbs, adjectives, and adverbs. Most root morphemes take suitable suffixes to allow them to serve in all four categories. For example, P. N. Johnson-Laird and Keith Oatley stated "fear" is both a noun and a transitive verb as in Uzbek "qo'rquv", "qo'rqmoq", but it is also the root of certain adjectives, "fearful" (qo'rqinchli), "fearless" (qo'rqmas), and "fearsome" (qo'rqinchli), and their corresponding adverbs, "fearfully", "fearlessly", and "fearsomely". These adverbs have also been turned into nouns: "fearfulness" (qo'rqoqlik), "fearlessness" (mardlik), and "fearsomeness" (qo'rqoqlik). At the root of all of these terms is the same morpheme expressing the same basic emotion. The interpretation of the suffixes is straightforward. They attribute the emotion or its denial to an individual, or they attribute the power of causing it to an individual; they map these notions into a manner of performance; and finally they convert these manners of performance into abstract properties [3].

In general, we treat only one or two forms of a word, and we do not attempt to deal with all the other morphological variants into which the same root enters. In some cases, however, there are changes in the interpretation of words formed from the same underlying root. In its emotional sense, P. N. Johnson-Laird and Keith Oatley give their example, the verb "affect" in Uzbek "ta'sirini o'tkazmoq" and its participle "affecting" "ta'sir o'tkazish" denote the power of moving the emotions, but the noun "affection" "mehtirbonlik, muhabbat" denotes the narrower concept of an attachment towards someone or something. There are other shifts of this sort. Now we compare the following pairs for instances of the phenomenon with the Uzbek language: "lovable" - "lovely" "yoqimli, dilbar" - "yoqimli", "dread" - "dreadful" "qo'rqinch" - "dahshatli", "awe" - "awful" "qo'rqish" - "qo'rqinchli". They determined that the second member of each pair does not denote an emotional state. Likewise, there is no guarantee of the productivity of a certain suffix, e.g. "hate" "nafratlanmoq" yields "hateful"

“jirkanch, nafratni keltiradigan” but not “hatesome”. Where a root yields different words with different emotional meanings, then they analysed both of them.

We have approached the everyday language of emotions according to the theory, which rests on empirical basis from outside the linguistic domain, and we tried to show how the different components of the theory are reflected in the words that are used to describe emotional experiences. This language and its underlying conceptual apparatus is intimately connected with the real nature of emotions, and the meanings of emotional words are neither arbitrary nor unanalysable but can relate to experience. The semantic field is based on the five emotional basic emotions, and words that refer solely to them have no any internal semantic structure-the modes are primitive and unanalysable conditions, at least from the standpoint of normal mental processing. There are terms that denote complex emotions that depend on cognitive evaluations depending on the model of the self.

Phraseological units are word-groups with a completely changed meaning, i.e. the meaning of the unit does not correspond to the meanings of its constituent parts. They are motivated, their meanings can be deduced from the meaning is based, is clear and transparent.

There are other ways to take context into account. Wilson. T., Wiebe. J., & Hoffmann. P. began with a lexicon compiled from other resources, but rather than directly classifying a sentence as positive/negative based on this lexicon, they first classified the sentence as simply neutral/polar based on the presence of “strongly” or “weakly” subjective parts in their lexicon [4]. Then all phrases that were marked as polar were disambiguated from their context (positive/negative/both/neutral). It permitted them to build in a number of things that really do make a difference in the interpretation of the words: for example, local negation (*not good, yaxshi emas*), longer-distance proposition negation (*it doesn't look very good, bu yaxshi ko'rinmayapti*), subject negation (*no one thinks that it's good, hech kim buni yaxshi deb o'ylamaydi*), diminishers (*little good, sal yaxshi*), word sense (*Environmental Trust vs. They trust him, Ular unga ishonishadi*), and like these things. What is surprising, given all of the features they include is that classifications using only the word tokens (and their positive/negative polarity) outperformed the others by a number of measures.

Now we note and analyze some phraseological units which expressing human spiritual state in the English and Uzbek languages according to the basic emotions. We took some of them from OALD:

Idioms with *happy*:

a happy event- bola tug'ilganda;

a/the happy medium- ikkita yo'ldan birini tanlash yoki ikkita tanlov o'rtasida qolish;

not a happy bunny- yoqimsiz vaziyatga tushgan odam;(but if we translate it word by word it means in Uzbek "baxtli/omadli quyon emas")

She wasn't a happy bunny at all [5].

many happy returns (of the day)- tug'ilgan kunida biror kishiga baxt tilashda foydalaniladi.

Phraseological units which belong to the semantic field of *joy Brighten up* –if we analyze this phrase *brighten* is “*yoritmoq*” in Uzbek, and cause it is a phrase we can translate it as *chehrasini ochmoq* but there is no word here *chehra* as *face* in English.

Cheer smb up- even though there is no word for *ko'ngil* – soul in this phrase its Uzbek equivalent is *ko'ngilni ko'tarmoq* We can also translate it as *kimnidir xursand qilmoq*

Get carried away- o'zini yo'qotmoq (quvonchdan) Jump at- if we translate it word by word it would be *sakramoq* but it can be suitable Uzbek equivalent of *bajonu dil rozi bo'lmoq* Following phrases belong to the semantic field of *depression, sadness, guilt*

Be hang up – if we translate this idiom as *osilmoq* it would be false from phraseological point of view. *Tashvish tortmoq* can be the Uzbek equivalent of this phrase.

Tear apart- here this idiom would be *bo'laklab yirtib tashlamoq* but suitable equivalent is *o'zini o'zi yeb bitirmoq*.

Break down – if we translate it word by word the translation would be *sinmoq, chil-chil qilmoq, parchalamoq* but it has an emotional meaning in Uzbek as *o'zini qo'lga ololmaslik* and these phrases *tear apart, break down, be hang up* can belong to the semantic fields of *depression, sadness, guilt*. *take somebody/something by surprise* – it means to attack or capture somebody/something unexpectedly or without warning and Uzbek equivalent can be *kapalagini uchirib yubormoq* and this idiom is considered semantic field of *surprise*.

to somebody's satisfaction – *ishonchiga kirmoq/ishonchini qozonmoq* and the idiom *earn someone's trust* can be the equivalent of *to somebody's satisfaction* and *in somebody's trust*.

in the trust of somebody – being taken care of by somebody and translation is *kimningdir ishonchida bo'lmoq, g'amxo'rligida bo'lmoq* and this idiom can be synonym of the idioms *earn someone's trust, to somebody's satisfaction* and *in somebody's trust*.

It is also suggested, that idioms in general have very much in common with quotations from literary sources, some of which also exist some idiomatic ready-

made units with a specialized meaning of their own. Such quotations, which have acquired specialized meaning and idiomatic value differ little from proverbs and sayings, which may be also regarded as quotations from the English folklore and are the part of this particularly brunch of literary studies [6].

What obscures the relatively common structure of the semantic field is the diversity of terms that include an emotional component. Likewise, the divergent analyses of emotional terminology to be found in the literature are a consequence, not of the absence of underlying order, but of the use of various methodologies lacking any simple theory of emotions. Previous investigates have also erred by including components that are not truly emotions, such as characteristics of behaviour like *cruelty*, *aggression*, and *vehemence*. Although some of the details of our account may have to be revised, we have corroborated our three major predictions.

Emotional terms relate to an organized semantic field, and are not an incoherent assemblage of terms. Their meanings depend on the five basic emotional modes. They divide up into coherent categories containing words denoting basic emotions, emotional relations, caused emotions, causes of emotions, emotional goals, and complex emotions.

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